

DEFORMATION MONITORING OF AN ELASTOMER USING FIBER-OPTIC STRAIN RATE SENSOR

K. Uzawa, K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, I. Ohsawa, M. Kanai

*Department of Environmental and Ocean Engineering, The University of Tokyo,
7-3-1Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8656, Japan*

SUMMARY: We verified the applicability of the new fiber-optic sensor to deformation monitoring of the seal equipped with an air cushion vehicle such as a surface effect ship (SES). The seal is a membrane structure made of an elastomeric material. It is difficult to measure deformation or vibration of the membrane structures by using a sensor fixed on it. When we use an electrical strain gage or an acceleration pickup, the stiffness of the sensor itself and the influence of its mass would frequently cause any problems.

In this study, we developed a new fiber-optic sensor with meandering shape to detect a strain rate derived from a fiber deformation, which is adequate to large deformable materials.

In simulation test with small model of the seal, vibration and deformation of seal can be monitored by this new fiber-optic sensor, and the results of measurement coincides with to the visual observation of variety in accordance with test condition

KEYWORDS: air cushion vehicle, membrane structure, deformation monitoring, fiber-optic sensor, strain measurement, vibration.

INTRODUCTION

An elastomeric material is used in various purposes as for automotive, robot, information transmission and aero-space vehicle. Recently an utilization of elastomer to the membrane structure object is increasing. When we use an elastomeric membrane as a structural material, it is important to know its mechanical character and a reaction against the external force. But as an elastomeric membrane has a strong non linear characteristic and a deformation is big, so that forecast of motion by analytically and a measurement of deformation using a sensor which is fixed on it are not easy. Especially when we use an electrical strain gage or an acceleration pickup to measure the deformation of the membrane material, the stiffness of the sensor itself and the influence of its mass would frequently cause any problems.

Also, The world largest air cushion vehicle; Tecno Super Liner(TSL) developed by the Mitsui Zosen will be placed in service between Tokyo and Ogasawara in autumn of 2005. The TSL is 140m in full length ,740 customers, maximum capacity loading of 210 tons, and the maximum speed of 39 knots. With TSL, an air cushion system is set up using a shield called a seal or a skirt which is fixed at the bow and the stern of a catamaran, and the air continuously being pumped into the pressure space make the ship floating. As a ship floats, it can go planing with less resistance. This seal utilizes a elastomeric material. Fig.1 shows a bow seal modle. A seal expands and contracts continuously by contacting the tip of seal to

the surface of sea, and is being wear and tear so rapidly that frequent inspections and changes are necessary.

The main factor of seal wear is assumed as a flageration, high-frequency vibration. Adequate understanding of phenomenon takes an important part to reveal the wearing mechanism.

But usual sensors like an acceleration pick up and a elctorical strain gage are not durable under the relentless condition, and it is difficult to get enough data to examine. Any sensors which can be durable enough under a demanding condition of seal usage will available not only to reveal the wear mechanism, but also to apply for a wear monitoring of a real ship.

So we verified a method to measure a deformation or vibration of the elastomer using a fiber-optic strain rate sensor. A fiber-optic strain rate sensors have been used for the structural health monitoring of a vessel and an acoustic emmission(AE) for architectural structure[1,2,3]. In this study, we used a new fiber-optic sensor with meandering shape to detect a strain rate derived from a fiber deformation combined to elastomar.

In this paper, we point out the applicability of fiber-optic strain rate sensor to an elastomic material, which has not been applied before and we confirmed that a fiber-optic sensor bonded to seal material can defect well a condition of deformation and vibration.

Fig. 1: Schematic of Bow Seal

A FIBER-OPTIC STRAIN RATE SENSOR WITH MEANDERING SHAPE

Shape of sensor part

Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide (DEFEW) can measure directly a strain rate, which is deformation speed of area where a sensor is fixed on [4]. We have been developed the DEFEW in shape of sensor as a straight line shape or a circle shape. Especially a circular loop sensor is a sensor which an optical fiber is coiled several times in a concentric fashion, when attached to a metal or concrete structure, it can measure AE with extremely high sensitivity and wide frequency range. This is because the sensitivity is proportional to the length of fiber at a sensor part.

As the elastic modulus of seal material is lower very much than grass-fiber and a circular loop sensor make rigidly the material around circle on a strain, a motion cannot detect correctly.

We develop the optical fiber sensor with meandering shape to avoid influence of the stiffness of the sensor itself[5]. (See the left of Fig. 2.)

The feature of this meandering shape sensor is as follows,

- (1) Less bit contribution to stiffness
- (2) Expandable for the big deformation

- (3) Directional sensitivity
- (4) Free from a shear strain

Fig. 2: Sensor figures with meandering shape

Fig. 3: Outlook of Sensor part

Adhesive Method of Optical Fiber

The seal material of air cushion vehicle, shown in Fig.3, is a reinforced urethane rubber with nylon weaving cloth.

We embedded a single mode optical fiber of 150μm in diameter with polyimid coating on the seal material. Soldering tip was used for implanting the fiber into the surface of seal material by melting with heat. For protection, thin rubber sheet, 0.3mm thick and 40mm square size, same material, was bonded upon the optical fiber with rubber bond. Fig.4 shows the cross section of sensor part.

Fig. 4: Picture of the seal material

Fig. 5: Cross section of a specimen and the seal material in which sensors were embedded

Doppler Effect in DEFEW and Setup of Measurement System

In the measurement system of DEFEW shown in Fig.6, the both ends of optical fiber including sensor part are connected to the Laser Doppler Velocimeter (LDV). Light source is He-Ne laser (output power; 1mW, wavelength. λ_0 : 632.8 nm), and heterodyne interference technique is applied to the measurement in the present paper.

When a sensor part shown in Fig.6 was combined in an object to be measured, an optical fiber strains according to a deformation of object. An incident light through a sensor transmitted and observed Doppler frequency shift f_D at detector. This frequency shift is proportional to fluctuation of finite overall length, L .

$$f_D = -\frac{f_0 n_{eq}}{c_0} \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (1)$$

,where f_0 is a lightwave frequency of incident, c_0 is a light speed in a vacuum, n_{eq} is an equivalent refractive index of an optical fiber.

The output of LDV(V1002) in present paper, v is expressed as follows;

$$v = \frac{c_0}{2f_0} f_D \quad (2)$$

Now we use sensitivity coefficient as; $v=sV$, then the strain rate of fiber at sensor dL/dt is expressed as follows;

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = -\frac{2sV}{n_{eq}} \quad (3)$$

When the sensor configuration is shown in left of Fig.2 , call vertical type meandering sensor, uniform strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_x, \dot{\epsilon}_y$ and dL/dt can express as follows

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \left(-3 + \frac{7\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) r \dot{\epsilon}_x + \left\{ \left(-1 + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) r + l \right\} \dot{\epsilon}_y \quad (4)$$

As the right of Fig.2 , call cross type meandering sensor, the sensor which axis of sensor is in x direction call sensor 1, in y direction call sensor 2, and output of each sensor express V_1, V_2 . then (3), (4) is as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 &= -\frac{n_{eq}}{2s} \left[\left(-3 + \frac{7\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) r \dot{\epsilon}_x + \left\{ \left(-1 + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) r + l \right\} \dot{\epsilon}_y \right] \\ V_2 &= -\frac{n_{eq}}{2s} \left[\left\{ \left(-1 + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) r + l \right\} \dot{\epsilon}_x + \left(-3 + \frac{7\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) r \dot{\epsilon}_y \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$n_{eq}=1.46, s=5(\text{mm/s/V}), r=8(\text{mm}), l=0(\text{mm})$ lease (6) finally[5].

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_x \\ \dot{\epsilon}_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -0.17 & 0.10 \\ 0.10 & -0.17 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The deformation in direction x and y can get by integration.

Fig. 6: Schematic of the measurement system with a sensing fiber and Laser Doppler Velocimeter (LDV)

Calibration of a fiber-optic sensor at a Cyclic tensile Test

In a Cyclic tensile test in the laboratory, the applicability of meandering sensor for a vibration and deformation monitoring of a seal material was examined.

Test Method

3 type of rectangular specimens; One piece of aluminum alloy(6063) as 1.9 mm thick plate and two pieces of seal material, were prepared for test (Ref. Table1). An aluminum specimen was measured with vertical type meandering sensor, one seal material specimen was with vertical type meandering sensor(OFS) and another with cross type meandering sensors(OFS(L),OFS(T)). Extensometer of 25mm gage length (EX25) and a strain gage (C-SG; gage length 3mm, base length ϕ 11mm) were used to calibrate a strain of every specimen. A cross strain gage(C-SG(L),C-SG(t)) was used for an aluminum specimen and an extensometer for seal ones. Extensometer was bonded at the point of foot to test specimens with cyanoacrylate adhesive for strain gage.

Sinusoidal tensile cyclic load was applied to the specimen with electro-hydraulic testing machine. The frequency and max displacement of cyclic loads were varied by each specimens. Table 2 shows the frequency and max. displacement with the specimen #1 to #3.

Table 1: Specimens in tensile tests

#	Material	Sensor orientation	Size (mm)		
			L	W	t
1	Al alloy	Longitudinal	150	25	1.9
2	Seal	Longitudinal	200	40	2.4
3	Seal	Cross			

Table 2: Load frequency and maximum displacement of each specimen

Freq. (Hz)	Max. displacement (mm)		
	#1	#2	#3
5	0.10	-	-
10	0.10	0.25	0.25
15	-	0.25	0.25
20	0.10	0.25	0.25
	0.15		
	0.20		
30	0.10	0.25	0.25
		0.38	0.38
		0.48	0.48
40	0.10	0.15	0.15
50	0.10	0.15	0.15
60	-	0.15	0.15

Test Result

Output signal of the fiber-optic sensor was integrated to the strain from the strain rate of itself. Fig.7 shows the converted strain data on the direction of load from fiber-optic sensor OFS and from C-SG(L) under the condition of frequency 20Hz and max.displacement 0.1 mm with an aluminum specimen.

Fig. 8 shows the strain data of OFS and extensometer on the direction of load with a seal specimen #2 under the condition of frequency of 30Hz and max. displacement of 0.25mm.

At last, the data for Fig. 9 is strain data from OFS(L),OFS(T) and extensometer measuring a seal specimen #3 under the condition of frequency 30Hz and max. displacement of 0.25mm. The detected ratio of a strain from fiber-optic sensor and strain gage with various frequency and max. displacement of specimen #3 is shown in Fig.10 and Fig.11.

Fig. 7: Strain measured by OFS(L) and strain gage (specimen: #1, frequency: 20Hz, max. displacement: 0.10mm)

Fig. 8: Strain measured by OFS(L) and extensometer (specimen: #2, frequency: 30Hz, max. displacement: 0.25mm)

Fig. 9: Strain measured by OFS(L) and extensometer (specimen: #3, frequency: 30Hz, max. displacement: 0.25mm)

Fig. 10: A plot of sensitivity against the Frequency of specimen #3

Fig. 11: A plot of sensitivity against max. displacement of specimen #3

Discussion of Results

The strain of aluminum specimen measured by vertical type meandering sensor was estimated less than 90% of the rate of strain gage. The coefficient is nearly constant with varies of frequency and max. displacement change. This coefficient is led by theoretically from a shape of sensor part, a sensitivity coefficient of measuring system and the poisson ratio of specimen and one or some of these are supposed to be an incidence of influence working to the error. The calibration coefficients of seal material specimen were evaluated respectively less than 30% and 20% for vertical and cross type meandering sensor. As cross type meandering sensor has some region of fibers overlap, some influence is considered to the stiffness of specimen. The optical fiber has much higher elastic coefficient than the seal material, the strain near the sensor part is constrained. Nevertheless the coefficient of seal material is lower than of aluminium one, the sensitivity is realized at almost constant level as the single axis strain gage for low elasticity material. It is suitable for measurement for seal material with this sensor, and confirmed the capability of monitoring for a vibration and deformation of seal.

Vibration and Deformation Monitoring of Seal Model

A vibration and deformation monitoring for seal model of an air cushion vessel was examined with meandering sensor.

Test Method

A seal model specimen was attached on the test equipment (Fig.12) to simulate the planing of vehicle at the Akishima Laboratory of Mitsui Zosen. A pump emitted a water jet from the tank below and spray from a nozzle to the tip of seal specimen. The inner pressure(cushion pressure) of the test model was supplied by another blower.

A seal model specimen has 4 cross type meandering sensors as shown in Fig.13. Each sensor was embedded as sensor 1 aligned against flow direction.

The test condition was varied the cushion pressure(P), water jet speed(V_f) and contact length (L_s). Table 3 shows the test conditon.

Fig. 12: Schematic of the test equipment sensor

Fig. 13: Lower seals with fiber-optic sensor

Table 3: Specimen and test conditions in test cases

Case	Specimen	P (kPa)	V_f (m/s)	L_s (mm)
1	2	2	20.0	200
2		2	20.0	150
3		2	10.0	100
4		2	15.0	100
5		2	20.0	100
6		4	20.0	100
7		6	20.0	100

Results

Example of the detected vibration, converted from strain rate of sensor A1 and A2 in case 6, is shown in Fig.13(a). Fig.13(b) gives the power spectra of strain waveform. Fig.14(a) shows the dependence of RMS on different cushion pressure. When a cushion pressure was at 6kPa, a big flatter was occurred at the skirt of seal and the optical fiber of sensor A and C were broken. (b) and (c) are the RMS change depending on the difference of flow speed and seal contact length.

(a) Strain measured by A1 and A2

(b) Power spectra of strain data

Fig. 13: Measurement results in the case 2

(a) RMS in different pressures, P

(b) RMS in different velocities, V

(c) RMS in different lengths, L

Fig. 14: Comparison between RMS of strain measured by the fiber optic sensors

Discussion of Results

In Fig.13, strain waveform of x direction sensor(A1) and y direction(A2) of cross type meandering sensors has an opposite phase. The observation of a power spectra leads to a result that a strain changed at 130Hz. These are the results of case 2, but a same result was examined at the flow speed of 20m/s. With decreasing flow speed, the amplitude of strain waveform is big, and several peaks appear in lower frequency zone in power spectra. This indicates a flatter at the skirt of seal which was observed in case 3 and 4.

Fig.14 shows influence on the amplitude of strain waveform by the difference of test condition. Fig.14(a) shows that an amplitude of strain get bigger in accordance with an increase of cushion pressure. And when the water speed gets slow, amplitude of the strain of sensor A and C, which is fixed at the tip of seal contacted with the water jet, gets particularly bigger, So that RMS changed like (b). IN case of seal contact length has 200mm, all sensors places at the contact zone of skirt shown in fig 11(b) and RMS increased likes (c).

It can conclude that a vibration and deformation of seal can be monitored by a fiber optic sensor, and behavior of seal changes in accordance with test condition. The measurement

results were consistent with the visual observation. It indicates the capability of inspecting any change of length of seal caused by wear.

Conclusions

The applicability of optical fiber to an elastomeric material has not been examined. One of the results of this study is indicate the applicability of a fiber-optic sensor to a vibration and deformation monitoring for elastomeric and big deformation material such as a seal material of air cushion vessel. And it is also indicated a capability that a seal vibration and deformation change widely by the planing condition and the movement of seal wear.

Therefore a practical use of vibration and deformation monitoring by a fiber optic sensor leads to an effective maintenance and control of seal. In that case, the durability of this sensor would be a next assignment.

REFERENCES

1. H. Murayama, K. Kageyama, I. Kimpara, T. Suzuki, I. Ohsawa and M. Kanai, "Fundamental Study on Smart Structure Approach to Marine Structure", *Bulletin of the Society of Naval Architects of Japan*, Vol. 184, 1998, pp. 513-522.
2. H. Murayama, K. Kageyama, H. Naruse, A. Simada and K. Uzawa, "Application of Fiber-Optic Distributed Sensors to Health Monitoring for Full-Scale Composite Structures", *Journal of Smart Intelligent Materials Systems and Structures*, Vol.14, No.1, 2003, pp.3-13
3. K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, I. Ohsawa, M. Kanai, K. Nagata, Y. Machijima and F. Matsumura, "Acoustic Emission Monitoring of a Reinforced Concrete Structure by Applying New Fiber-Optic Sensors", *Smart Materials and Structures*,14, Institute of Publishing, , 2005, (printing).
4. K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, I. Ohsawa, M. Kanai, T. Motegi, K. Nagata, Y. Machijima and F. Matsumura, "Development of a New Fiber-Optic Acoustic/Vibration Sensor: Principle, Sensor Performance, Applicability to Health Monitoring and Characteristics at Elevated Temperature", *Structural Health Monitoring 2003*, DEStech Publications, PA, 2003, pp.1150-1157.
5. K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, I. Ohsawa, K. Uzawa, M. Kanai, T. Ogawa, A. Imakita, S. Ono., "Fundamental Study on Deformation Monitoring of Vibrating Seals in Air Cushion Vehicles by Using Fiber-Optic Sensors", *Bulletin of the Society of Naval Architects of Japan*, Vol. 193, 2004, pp. 141-150.